

SOIL COMPACTION BOOSTS GREENHOUSE GAS N₂O

FACT

N₂O is the strongest greenhouse gas and it comes mainly from agricultural soils

EFFECT

Topsoil compaction increases N₂O emissions by up to 42 times

HELP

Mitigation strategies aim to loosen the soil and recover pore system functionality

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Uncompacted soil

Compacted soil

Oxygen needed

Traffic and animal-induced compaction can lead to an increased N₂O emissions by decreasing soil oxygen supply. How this happens is discussed in this review.

EJP SOIL INNOVATION HIGHLIGHTS

Foto: M. Gerzabek

TOWARDS CLIMATE-SMART SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF AGRICULTURAL SOILS

EJP SOIL is a European Joint Programme on Agricultural Soil Management addressing key societal challenges including climate change and future food supply. <https://ejpsoil.eu/>

The goal is to improve the understanding of agricultural soil management by finding synergies in research, strengthening research communities and raising public awareness.

1100+ experts, 24 countries, addressing multiple aspects of soil management across different European agroecosystems.

EJP SOIL FUNDED PROJECT TRACE SOIL

The project aim is to identify the mechanisms underpinning trade-offs and synergies of soil carbon sequestration, greenhouse gas emissions and nutrient losses in agricultural soils across Europe, and propose climate-zone specific indicators and measures to mitigate trade-offs.

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TARGET EJP SOIL EXPECTED IMPACT AND EU MISSION SOIL OBJECTIVES

Understanding of soil management for climate change mitigation, adaptation, sust production & sustainable environment

Mission SOIL: Improve soil structure to enhance soil biodiversity

HIGHLIGHT FACTS FROM:

EJP SOIL project
TRACE SOIL

Applicability:
all climatic zones according to
Metzger et al. (2005)
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-822X.2005.00190.x>

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